
AN ASSESSMENT OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ADVANTAGED AND DISADVANTAGED GROUP

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Abstract

The economic development is the prime drive of prosperous human life. Traditionally, Indian society is represented by glaring inequality among different social groups. Traditionally, Scheduled Castes (SC) is considered one of the most economically disadvantaged social groups in Indian society, on the other hand, High-Castes having the privilege of economic prosperity in their life. The present study is an attempt to analyze the economic status of advantaged i.e. High Castes and disadvantaged group i.e. Scheduled Castes across India. This research paper is a quantitative work based on primary data surveyed from eight states across India. The principal component analysis has been done for assessing the levels of economic development of the households. A PCA score has been computed from different economic variables to analyse the spatial pattern of economic development by using geo-spatial technology. Comparative spatial analysis of economic status for both social groups reveals that there is a large spatial disparity in the level of economic development across India. However, the economic statuses of privileged high castes are too much better in comparison to disadvantaged across the spatial disparity.

Keywords: *Economic-Status, High-Caste (HC), India, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Scheduled Castes (SC), Spatial-Variation.*

Introduction

The economic status of the household members plays a key role in accelerating the process of growth in all aspects of an individuals' life. There is a major two division in every society of economic prosperity i.e. haves and have-not. The socioeconomic statuses of an individual have

been engrained in the hierarchal social structure of Indian society. In Indian society, the economic status of an individual is determined by their gender, castes, class, region, and region. There are a number of restrictive social as well as traditional laws that direct to individuals' mode of economic activities and occupation in order to gain an economic status in society. Thus, socio-economic factors play an important role in access to occupation and mode of production based on labor divisions of the hierarchal structure of the Indian society. Resultantly, Scheduled Castes belongs to a very poor socio-economic background; their educational and occupational aspirations were very low (Ganqgrade, 1974). Scheduled Castes are found to be inferior in the socio-economic background (Aikara, 1980). Most of the problems confronted by the Scheduled Castes have their origins in their prolonged backwardness and isolation due to their caste status. An underlying factor that makes these problems very prominent is their relatively poor background. Though many among them have been able to make a significant break with their past status and role, they betray a total dependence on the government to provide them security. Thanks to their education, these students are more conscious of life as compared to their caste brethren and they identify the land-holding caste as the exploiting and oppressive elements (Dreze, and Kingdom, 1999). Historically, Scheduled Castes and women have found the bottom-most place in Indian society. The social and economic backwardness of Scheduled Castes is the function of their traditionally lower position in the social hierarchy (Chauhan, 1975). Indian society has been described as a “compartmentalized” society as it has a vast number of groups that maintain distinct and diverse styles of life. The system by which these groups are related and mutually accommodated is so complex as to defy general description (Galanter, 1984).

The present study is an attempt to examine the economic differences between an advantaged i.e. high-castes and disadvantaged group i.e. Scheduled castes across India. The economic status of the surveyed household from both the social groups has been presented in terms of economic activities in which household member was engaged in order to earn money and other economic wealth for smooth life across India. The paper also presents an account of regional variation in levels of economic development for both social groups across the surveyed states of India. The present article can be divided into three major segments i.e. level of economic development, spatial analysis of economic status and discussion. Largely, paper quantifies the economic status to make a comparison between advantaged and disadvantaged social groups.

Database and Research Methodology

The present study is based on primary household data collected from field surveys across the eight states in India. A total of 603 household samples had been interviewed with a set of structured questionnaires representing the population of 40 villages from eight states of India. For assessment of the levels of economic status, a composite index of five economic variables has been developed through the computation of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) score for the particular districts in order to analyze the spatial variation between High-Castes and Low

castes (Scheduled Castes). The principal component analysis is the method of index creation offers a technique that conglomerates several components into one indicator so that the index will be as similar as possible with respect to all the component characteristics that were synthesized into one or a few indexes (Abdi & Williams, 2010). In other words, PCA is a multivariate technique for analysing a data table in which observations are described by several inter-correlated quantitative dependent variables. It combines a large number of variables into a few numbers of conceptual variables (Jolliffe, 1986). Computer package SPSS 21 facilitates a calculation facility of Principal Component Analysis scores for a given distribution (NUEPA, 2009).

Table-1										
Properties of PCA Composite Score of Family Economic Development Index (FEDI)										
SL	PCA Index	Vari-ables	KM O =0.6 Min.	BTS = p<0.05	CC = > 0.3 % & many	Eige nval ue => 1	Scre e Plot	Cmpnt. Explain s	Cmpnt. Extrac- ted	Rotatio n Solution
1	Schedule d Castes	6	0.644	0.000	Many	3	>1	35.885	First	Varimax
2	High Castes	6	0.595	0.000	Many	2	>1	31.499	First	Varimax

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

A total of 603 household samples have been utilized for analysis and constructing PCA scores for the surveyed districts. The 40 location i.e. villages make 40 different cases across the country. So, 40 cases (N=40) with the different number of variables for separate PCA index have been mention in table 1. In this way, PCA composite indices have been constructed fulfilling the necessary conditions of Principal Component Analysis.

Status of Family Economic Development

The socioeconomic status of the family has a strong effect on students' academics and another achievement in life (Tomul and Polat, 2013). The household having larger landholding size have a better chance to be overpass poor/poverty over non-poor reduce significantly (Joshi, 2012). By increasing the improvement in the socio-economic status of workers the economic opportunity can be improved in order to reduce inequality (Bernanke, 2008). The economic status of a family

plays a major role in achieving a prosperous and wealthy life. To measure the economic status of surveyed households a composite index (*Family Economic Development Index-FEDI*) of the proportion of casual labor, regular wage/ salaried, self-employed, retired/pension, public/executive job and availability of land has been used to show the regional pattern and comparison between high castes and scheduled castes groups.

Scheduled Castes (Disadvantaged Group)

Economic status of scheduled castes' show that 16% of the surveyed scheduled castes population were engaged in daily wage casual laborer, 8% were working with regular wage or salaried in private sector, 5% were self-employed, 1% was retired or pensioner and, 3% were working either in government sector or at the post of executive employee in a private sector. There is only 20% of the scheduled castes' families having their own agricultural land. Remaining scheduled Castes families belong to the landless category (Appendix-1).

Regarding the economic status of scheduled castes' families, district Bengaluru Rural has recorded the highest FEDI score with 2.48 followed by Bijnor and S.24 Parganas; while on the other hand, Mallapuram (-1.63) stand at the bottom level of economic development preceded by SPS Nellore and Uttara Kannada. The economic status of scheduled castes (Map-1) shows that most of the districts of northern states come under the high or medium level of economic development; while on the other hand majority of districts in southern states fall under a low level of economic status.

In northern states, 3 districts namely Mathura, Sonbhadra and South 24 Parganas come under the high level, 11 districts like Bikaner, Sitapur, and Murshidabad, etc. fall in medium level and, 6 districts like Bijnor, Samastipur, and Jalpaiguri, etc. comes under low level of economic development. On the other hand, in southern states, 15 districts like Nalgonda, Aurangabad, and Mallapuram, etc. fall in low level, 4 districts like Latur, Anantapur, etc. comes under medium level and only one district of Bengaluru Rural falls under the high level of economic development (Appendix-1).

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

High-Castes (Non-Reserved Castes)

Economic status of High-Castes families reveals that only 1% of High-Castes population were engaged in daily wage casual laborer, 11% were working with regular wage or salary in private sector, 13% were self-employed, 3% were retired or pensioner, 16% were working either in government sector or at the post of executive employee in a private sector. There are a total of 88% of the High-Castes families having their own agricultural land; an insignificant proportion of the total High Castes families come under landless families (Appendix-2).

The economic development status of High-Castes shows that the district Alappuzha has recorded the highest FEDI score with 2.82 followed by Bengaluru Rural and Ernakulam; while on the other hand, Mathura (-2.00) stand at the bottom level of economic development preceded by Aurangabad and Nalgonda. The economic status of non-reserved (Map-2) show that total 6 districts like Kannur, Bengaluru, and Bikaner, etc. registered high level, 26 Districts like Mathura, Barmer, and Thiruvananthapuram, etc. recoded medium level and, 8 districts like west Midnapore, Latur and Nalgonda, etc. recorded low level of economic development (Appendix-2).

Discussion

The analysis of the spatial pattern of levels of economic development for both the social groups i.e. High-castes and scheduled castes suggests that there is spatial variation in the levels of economic status for social groups selected for the study. The economic status of Scheduled Castes in the Northern states is much better than the Southern states. Similarly, for the High-castes, northern states are much favorable than the Southern states. However, most of the surveyed districts for high-castes come either under the medium or high level of economic development (Map-2), while most of the districts for scheduled castes falls under low level of medium level economic development. The Map-1 and Map-2 show that different spatial patterns of economic status for both social groups. Most of the southern districts especially in Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, and Maharashtra fall under a low level of Scheduled Castes' economic development. The Map-2 of High-Castes' economic status reveals that most of the surveyed area come under the medium and high level of economic development except Andhra Pradesh and Maharashtra. Thus, the economic status of scheduled castes is lower than the high-castes across the surveyed districts.

The comparative analysis of the levels economic development between high-castes and scheduled castes reveals that the largest proportion (16%) of Scheduled Castes population were engaged in daily wage casual laborer work and a small proportion were in regular wages, self-employed and in government sectors or on executive employees in private sectors. On the other hand, the majority (16%) of the High-Castes population we're working either in the government sector or at the post of the executive employee in the private sector. In the case of self-employed, regular wage/salaried and retired or pensioner High-Castes are also better than scheduled castes population. Moreover, only 20% of Scheduled Castes family have their own agricultural land; while 88% of High-Castes families having their own agricultural land. Thus, it clear those economic statuses of High-Castes are much better than Scheduled Castes in the study area (Appendix-1 & Appendix-2). Indian society is featured by social segregation and unashamed discriminations structured in the hierarchical social structure. As per the order of social hierarchy, Schedule Castes suffer at the lower strata where material deprivation and impurity reinforce one another (Beteille, 1998). Therefore, the social and economic conditions of scheduled castes remain as deprived and most of them are still engaged in low income-generating occupations like daily wage labourers and other menial works (Sinha, 1981).

The above discussion reveals for both the social groups that the Northern states are better than southern states. While only for Scheduled Castes, Northern states are much better than Southern states, especially Rajasthan is the best in Scheduled Castes' economic development. The economic status of High-Castes in Rajasthan, Kerala, Karnataka, Bihar, West Bengal, and Uttar Pradesh is best in comparison to the rest of the surveyed states. There are three most important points came out from this discussion, i) overall economic status of High-Castes are much better

than Scheduled Castes in the study area, ii) largely northern states are in better position in comparison to southern states for both the social groups, iii) the economic status High-Castes are good in all the surveyed states except Andhra Pradesh and Maharashtra. Thus it may say that the Scheduled Castes population across the surveyed districts has a lower possibility to enhance their social and economic status because, the socio-economically deprived backgrounds of an individual having accumulated less human capital during their family life because they become more cost-sensitive in all aspect of life (Declercq and Verboven, 2015).

Conclusion

Normally, northern states having a comparatively better status in economic conditions for both the social groups with few exceptions. However, district-level status varies from state to state differently for Scheduled Castes as well as High-Castes. The Scheduled Castes are considered one of the most backward segments of our society, which is evidently verified true in the light of primary data in terms of comparative analysis of economic status between High-Castes and Scheduled Castes across the study area. Normally, High-Castes households are much better in economic status in terms of engagement in secondary and tertiary economic activities and availability of agricultural land. While the majority of the Scheduled Castes family member is engaged in primary economic activities such as daily wage casual and marginal workers and are belong to landless families which brought them low economic status.

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Appendix

Appendix-1								
Status of Economic Development of Scheduled Castes Household								
S L	District	Casual Labor	Regular Wage/ Salaried	Self- Employed	Retired / Pension	Public/ Executive Job	Land	Family Economic Development Index (FEDI)
1	Ernakulam	22.45	8.16	2.04	2.04	4.08	0.00	-0.905
2	Thiruvananthapuram	22.73	9.09	4.55	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.634
3	Alappuzha	23.91	4.35	4.35	0.00	6.52	9.09	-0.747
4	Mallapuram	30.00	8.00	0.00	2.00	8.00	0.00	-1.634
5	Kannur	14.55	16.36	1.82	3.64	1.82	0.00	-0.224
6	Mysore	32.35	4.41	4.41	1.47	1.47	0.00	-1.352
7	Bengaluru Rural	4.17	13.89	15.28	0.00	0.00	50.00	2.479
8	Uttara Kannada	28.00	8.00	0.00	6.00	0.00	0.00	-1.396
9	Davanagere	14.81	7.41	7.41	0.00	5.56	50.00	0.813
10	Kalburagi	12.28	12.28	5.26	3.51	3.51	30.00	0.615
11	Anantapur	17.54	7.02	5.26	0.00	3.51	30.00	0.137
12	SPS Nellore	27.27	9.09	0.00	0.00	2.27	0.00	-1.411
13	Visakhapatnam	21.05	7.89	0.00	0.00	5.26	0.00	-1.063
14	Nalgonda	15.79	7.02	1.75	0.00	7.02	0.00	-0.580
15	Karimnagar	25.00	5.77	0.00	1.92	1.92	0.00	-1.309

16	Nagpur	17.65	15.69	0.00	0.00	1.96	0.00	-0.662
17	Latur	15.38	13.46	7.69	0.00	0.00	10.00	0.392
18	Kolhapur	22.64	15.09	1.89	1.89	3.77	10.00	-0.648
19	Pune	16.67	16.67	1.85	5.56	5.56	0.00	-0.361
20	Aurangabad	28.07	5.26	1.75	0.00	1.75	0.00	-1.353
21	Udaipur	4.76	7.14	10.71	2.38	3.57	10.00	1.248
22	Barmer	16.42	8.96	10.45	0.00	8.96	20.00	0.589
23	Bikaner	8.00	10.00	5.00	2.00	3.00	20.00	0.657
24	Ajmer	12.68	4.23	7.04	1.41	4.23	60.00	1.020
25	Alwar	15.49	7.04	2.82	2.82	2.82	30.00	0.052
26	Purulia	21.15	5.77	3.85	0.00	1.92	50.00	0.041
27	W. Midnapore	20.00	5.45	5.45	0.00	0.00	10.00	-0.293
28	S.24 Parganas	3.03	6.06	16.67	1.52	1.52	0.00	1.812
29	Murshidabad	14.00	0.00	14.00	0.00	2.00	40.00	1.280
30	Jalpaiguri	23.53	11.76	1.96	0.00	1.96	20.00	-0.622
31	Araria	16.00	4.00	4.00	0.00	8.00	30.00	0.007
32	Banka	23.68	2.63	3.95	0.00	0.00	20.00	-0.594
33	Samastipur	11.94	5.97	2.99	0.00	4.48	10.00	-0.061
34	W. Champaran	7.06	5.88	2.35	2.35	2.35	30.00	0.517
35	Rohtas	13.33	4.00	6.67	1.33	0.00	30.00	0.533
36	Gorakhpur	18.64	5.08	5.08	1.69	3.39	20.00	-0.117
37	Sonbhadra	9.72	6.94	8.33	0.00	5.56	81.82	1.688

38	Sitapur	22.22	6.17	4.94	0.00	0.00	60.00	0.255
39	Bijnor	17.98	7.87	3.37	0.00	0.00	20.00	-0.185
40	Mathura	1.19	9.52	10.71	1.19	5.95	40.00	1.928
	Total	16.39	7.83	5.22	1.12	3.05	19.85	0.090

Source: Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015

Appendix-2								
Status of Economic Development of High-Castes' Household								
S L	District	Casual Labor	Regular Wage/Salaried	Self-Employed	Retired/Pension	Public/Executive Job	Land	Family Economic Development Index (FEDI)
1	Ernakulam	0.00	26.32	0.00	5.26	36.84	100.00	1.914
2	Thiruvananthapuram	8.33	25.00	4.17	0.00	12.50	40.00	-1.068
3	Alappuzha	0.00	12.50	0.00	16.67	29.17	100.00	2.819
4	Mallapuram	0.00	8.00	4.00	4.00	28.00	100.00	1.149
5	Kannur	0.00	13.33	3.33	6.67	26.67	0.00	1.225
6	Mysore	0.00	31.58	0.00	0.00	26.32	40.00	0.680
7	Bengaluru Rural	0.00	7.69	0.00	11.54	38.46	100.00	2.691
8	Uttara Kannada	0.00	9.38	12.50	3.13	25.00	100.00	0.555

9	Davanagere	0.00	2.86	22.86	0.00	17.14	100.0 0	-0.621
10	Kalburagi	0.00	19.35	16.13	0.00	16.13	100.0 0	0.586
11	Anantapur	0.00	8.70	21.74	4.35	30.43	100.0 0	-0.380
12	SPS Nellore	0.00	9.09	18.18	4.55	22.73	100.0 0	0.372
13	Visakhapatnam	0.00	28.57	14.29	0.00	9.52	80.00	-0.662
14	Nalgonda	0.00	17.24	27.59	0.00	10.34	100.0 0	-1.137
15	Karimnagar	7.69	11.54	7.69	0.00	15.38	100.0 0	-0.898
16	Nagpur	0.00	21.21	12.12	0.00	15.15	100.0 0	-0.263
17	Latur	2.94	17.65	17.65	0.00	11.76	80.00	-1.012
18	Kolhapur	0.00	4.35	26.09	0.00	13.04	80.00	-0.994
19	Pune	0.00	8.57	11.43	2.86	17.14	100.0 0	0.177
20	Aurangabad	0.00	6.45	32.26	0.00	9.68	80.00	-1.410
21	Udaipur	0.00	10.26	12.82	5.13	12.82	80.00	0.128
22	Barmer	0.00	2.94	26.47	2.94	11.76	100.0 0	-0.700
23	Bikaner	0.00	5.88	5.88	11.76	11.76	100.0 0	1.149
24	Ajmer	0.00	6.06	12.12	3.03	15.15	80.00	0.028

25	Alwar	0.00	8.00	12.00	0.00	36.00	100.0 0	0.764
26	Purulia	0.00	5.71	31.43	2.86	11.43	60.00	-1.004
27	W. Midnapore	0.00	10.71	7.14	0.00	21.43	80.00	0.203
28	S.24 Parganas	0.00	10.53	21.05	5.26	10.53	60.00	-0.346
29	Murshidabad	0.00	20.00	12.00	0.00	16.00	100.0 0	-0.217
30	Jalpaiguri	3.13	3.13	12.50	3.13	18.75	100.0 0	-0.094
31	Araria	0.00	9.52	4.76	4.76	9.52	60.00	0.212
32	Banka	0.00	22.58	12.90	3.23	9.68	100.0 0	-0.197
33	Samastipur	2.94	17.65	11.76	5.88	5.88	80.00	-0.393
34	W. Champaran	0.00	5.26	15.79	0.00	13.16	100.0 0	-0.528
35	Rohtas	0.00	17.50	7.50	2.50	7.50	100.0 0	-0.173
36	Gorakhpur	0.00	4.65	11.63	2.33	16.28	100.0 0	0.062
37	Sonbhadra	2.86	12.86	1.43	5.71	12.86	100.0 0	0.399
38	Sitapur	0.00	20.00	8.57	0.00	8.57	100.0 0	-0.446
39	Bijnor	4.00	2.00	30.00	0.00	4.00	100.0 0	-1.991
40	Mathura	3.51	3.51	10.53	3.51	8.77	100.0 0	-0.505

	Total	1.01	11.35	13.06	3.03	15.55	87.50	-0.077
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Source:

1. Computed from Primary Data of Household Survey, 2015